

A STUDY ON DIGITAL MARKETING IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

In the World, Various Countries vary in economic, Socio-Political system . They are differed in economic- Commercial, marketing Systems. In Advanced Countries, marketing System, Sectorial growth, Productivity, income level, Consumption all are very high. But in the Backward Countries Economic-Commercial Variables are very weaker. Because of backwardness of all factors of production, low Marketing growth, low rate of Scientific and Technology. In India are developing Country. During 1990-91 onwards LPG Scheme drastically Changing the shape of our economy, commerce, trade, foreign exchange, Marketing Strategy. In traditional Marketing System, there is no rapid spread of goods and services. Because of lack of information, knowledge, quality, durability , taste, price and Communication.

In India, in 1990 ICT Revolution take place widely, Then all sectors adopting various Marketing Strategy. Marketing System need to upgrade, advanced, modified updates in every day. So that Digital Marketing System gradually Expanding across country.

Key words: Digital market, Digital consumers,/ Customers, Consumer- Culture, Digital Tools, Digital devices. Consumer Behaviors.

INTRODUCTION

From 1980, 1990's onwards Conventional Market weakening and Digital marketing Expanded in Urban and Rural area also. But in this state, basic facilities are differed in some regions. Like roads, Connectivity , Electricity, demand, price, income, culture behavior, literacy, knowledge and other factors are impacted on Digital Market.

Digital Market means

Digital Marketing includes the internet online based digital, DTP, Computer technologies, mobile phones. Digital media, and other modes are platforms to promote various products, goods and services to online customers. Now a days digital customers receiving goods and services at door steps. It's a fostering technological growth. In the ICT Sector: and development of a highly skilled workers. In the Digital Market. It avoid the visit of physical shops. In India digital Market widely spread in urban, semi-urban areas include rural areas. But rural people's are weaker in operative skill of digital devices in the Digital Market. Here Digital customers are called as Consumerism, psychologists, Sociologists, Anthropologist , Economists and other experts. They are may be choose use, reject dispose. Ect....

Digital India and Digital Market

During 2014, union Government was to encouraging Electronic governance in the country. Its objectives to make reducing the paperwork in the public- government interface and try to reduce corruption level in all sector. It connects the all with each other digital or Electronically . It enhance and improve the Connection of all regions like villages, urban, semi urban, remote control areas ect.. through the digital networks. It includes e-services,

improve transparency via. UPI, mobile enabled money transfers between bank accounts, and BHIM app for less cash Economy.

Theoretical Background for the study:-

Regarding Digital marketing various development theories are developed such as

1. **Dependency Theory:** This theory was developed by Raul prebisch in 1949. It states that the growing disenchantment with modernization theory, owing to its failure to explain growing inequalities. Here need to using an alternative paradigm. It focus on process of . Social, technical change was not gradual and evolutionary. It explain the relationship between the market depends on the other variables like, supply, digital devices and other factors. It's a experience of the European countries and Asian Countries.
2. **Big push Theory- Rodan's:** This Theory was developed in 1943. Its explains that, there is a at least minimum level of resources that must be devoted to a development strategies. If it is to have any chase of success. This theory proceeding 'Bit by Bit' will not add up in its effects to the sum total of the single bits. At least, minimum quantum of investment is a necessary though not sufficient condition of success. He finds there indivisibilities, such as supply of social overhead capital the indivisibility of demand, And indivisibility in supply of savings. They argues high quantum of investment is required to scale of commercial obstacles to development created by these indivisibilities. It applicable to producers to push Digital Market in broader to stable in global market.
3. **Theory of Consumer Behaviors-Alfred Marshall and Charles Glenn Walters :** This theory was developed by Alfred Marshall the study that, In digital Market, digital Consumers, online communities, mobile marketing, Digital Marketing tool box, content markets, all are takes a wide scope in global trade. In this market, the consumer attitudes, behavior is crucial for the expand or contrasting of the digital market. It focus on the how these consumers involve, interacts, response to the digital market strategies.
4. **Digital market is a journey it taken new type of markets.** It innovates, search the new type of opportunities in market system. Its a fastest moving and most exciting aspects of marketing in present market system. It has changed the relationship between business and customers. It influenced by acceleration in new technology.
5. **Theory of Innovation- Schultz:** This theory was developed by joseph schumpeter' in1979 the says theory of profits centers on the idea of that the entrepreneurs and investors or the Markets need to search now type of innovations, research, and discovery in the upcoming modern era. Because of peoples are seeking, searching new types, style, design, passion, advanced, model, new tastes in every thing. So that in the development era, innovation only takes places to get more and more profits and acquire market in the Competitive world. It provide new products, processes, new markets, organizational structures all these lead to increased the profits for the innovators and it create new opportunities in the market.
6. **Theory of Communication:** This theory was developed by John Robinson in 1976. According to him, where these media, digital communication was received by the influencer and then it passed to other individuals and groups. It's based on the one piece of research. It means that not necessarily generalizable to the other situations.

It's a simplistic binary model; more over this is how mass-media performed and spread across society. This model was extended from two to multiple steps.

7. Theory of Diffusion or Spread: This theory was developed by Everest Rogers in 1962. This theory based on two steps flow of communications and explored the conditions that increased or decreased the likelihood of product adoption. It focus on how a goods or products gains momentum and spreads through the group via digital or oral. Rogers has categorized the innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, laggards, which are considered the time at which on individual adopted in innovation. It influence product adoption. This theory more suitable to this article.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Books publication

One focusing as follows----- Reports, Books. Journals ect—

A.K.NAYAK(2003) Internet Technologies and Application “Dominant Publication and distributors

New Delhi:

1. 1.A K NAYAK(2003) In his book entitled ‘Internet Technology and Applications ‘ he has explains that the word of information: News, Entertainment infotainment, commerce and Business is truly unified under the global stage, dimensions of the internet and the digital aspects. The digital devices users are every also increasing. All of these digital customers to know the various digital/Internet technologies and different applications. So that they efficiently utilize their talents and digital knowledge.
2. James cohen and Thoman Kenny (2016) Entitled “ producing new and digital media” in this book, he states that the digital market is a technology has inevitably transformed our conventional media into a new media like digital media, internet, online ect. It's a multitude of interactive platforms in modern world. Now a days Digital market have the read, listened on mobile devices tablets, e-reader, flat screens and wearable devices particularly these are all are actively participate in different communities. Its called “Digital Environment”.
3. Steven Miles (1998) ‘Digital marketing is a consumerism”: In this journal the authors says that. The consumer culture is different in modern, digital world, they passonable modified, advanced in the purchasing style. Digital market observes the people via digital tools. Here the consumer's culture, marketing style, behavior, psychology, response all are modernized in global context. They are not interested to go to physical shop. Because of so many reasons like, par away, high risk, cost- benefit analysis.
4. Jagannath.K. Dango(2019) entitled “Influence of Technology on Market” In this book, author says that, now the trends are in humanities; commerce and sciences, is comprises of the products and the process. Created by the digital experts to meet our wants and necessities. In the market, Industries and Business promoters generally. Quick to adopt advanced and new technologies and software's in the market. Now a days Digital market has experienced with the technological innovations like online, internet, electrical devices. In the modern life, some technologies have become permanent part of digital market. It depends resources such as e-mail, internet, course-web- pages 5 and computer simulations.

5. Nelson (1980): Digital Marketing (1980): In his book he starts that, In the digital world, the content Marketing is a cornerstone of all the digital marketing operations. It may be words, photos, info graphics, videos, these are all increase broader visibility, drive traffic to websites. It may helps educate and Convert customers. According to 'Bill Gates', it's a entertainment sector and content is recognized as a cornerstone of digital market. Now it's a strategic marketing approach focusing on creating and distributing valuable, relevant and consistent content basis. Its attract, convert, retain customers its thinking and acting like a publishers.

Need for the Study

In the Digital market world, global transactions, national transactions are greater in modern world. So need to identify the cause and effects, cost-benefit analysis, and advantages, and disadvantages of digital marketing in market operations. This work try to attempts fill the gap in the literature of all the reviews.

Research Gap:

About 'Digital Marketing' empirical students attempted fill end of 2010-2019..... Several all previous research h project works are focusing on only other aspects other than. 'Digital Marketing'. There is no recent works, on the digital market, so that this full fill this gap.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:-

Regarding Digital Marketing, the following objectives have been formulated.

1. To Study about the importance of Technology in the market system.
2. To study about impact of digital, Technology on Market and consumers.
3. To know about the difference between traditional and modern technology in market.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

For the purpose of this article, some hypothesis are formulated.

1. 1. Most of the producers, Entrepreneurs would not have continued their business but for digital market if not existed .
2. 2. Faster regular and more transactions would not have takes place if the digital market exit in market .
3. 3. Most of the markets are facing serious problems like survivability in market.

The Traditional and Digital Marketing Tools

In the modern world, technology has going to decreased in price and with the development of the internet, digital market.

Traditional markets tools such as newspapers, Magazines, door to door sales peoples, company brochures, traditional public relations, directors, community groups.

Digital Marketing tools such as online adverts social media, pay-per-click, e-mail, websites online public relationships, blogs, search engine, social networks. Now a days it covers delivery, services, retail, financial services, consumer products, online super market ect.

DIGITAL MARKET IN INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

1. 1. In 1995-Amazon disrupted the traditional book sellers. But now in the digital market, it's a American multinational technology company it performed in e-commerce, cloud computing, online advertising, digital streaming, and AI adopted in

the digital market. And also alphabet, apple, meta, Microsoft all these are very dominant in global digital market. Its turn over US \$ 59.25 billion and its employees around 1.556.000 during 2024.

2. Netflix 1997: It's a traditional video hire market in USA. Now it's a technology company known for its subscription-based streaming service in world stage. It offers a variety of original and licensed movies, TV shows, documentaries, and anime, these provides via- various internet and connected devices through digital marketing.
3. Uber Taxi Service- It was founded in 2009. It adopted new type of technologies Inc, that developing the operator of taxi services through a mobile app, it connects riders with drivers for the ride-waiting services and also food delivery and freight transport. If operates across to countries and 10,000 cities in the world. Its turnover around \$10.54 billion. It create more and more employment opportunities in operative places.

Statistical view on Digital Market

During 2024, The Digital Market size was around USD 5.18 Billion.

The Market estimated to grow at a CARG of 30.20% during 2025-2034 to reach a value of USD.72.10 Billion by 2034.

Digital Media Spends Across Industry verticals

SL NO	Sectors	Percentage of spend
1	FMCG	34%
2	E-Commerce	27%
3	Consumer Durables	5%
4	Pharmaceuticals	5%
5	Auto	4%
6	Telecom	3%
7	Education	3%
8	BFSI	1%
9	Media Entertainment	1%
10	Retail	13%

Share of Digital Market; Insights

Search Engines- 33%

Mobile applications – 26%

The Status of Digital Market in Rural and Urban Areas

There are some obstacles, hurdles in the digital marketing system. India largely covered with village call rural areas. In rural, customers are low literacy level, traditional lifestyle, low per capita income of households and poor standard of living, backwardness of rural masses, low level of exposure of product category, variation in languages, seasonality of demand, mass communication problem banking and credit problems.

Advantages of Digital Markets

- It Eliminates the barriers to space and value of time, physical shopping .
- It encouraging shopping, consuming, purchasing in the market system.

- Digital market creates many many amazing opportunities for the seller and buyers.
- It avoid unnecessary risk of road trafficking cost, physical and mental stress of buyers.
- It improves interest of customers, of improve knowledge of products.

Disadvantages of Digital markets

There are Various disadvantages are found in the digital marketing in markets.

1. Information misuse/abusing data.
2. Privacy issues-collecting personal data's and selling in online.
3. Switching Barriers – difficult to switch provider.
4. Favoritism and discrimination – may be sharing of customer behavior to others .
5. Unfairness – High price and low price collection from customers.
6. Dishonesty – cross selling.
7. Financial penalties – Benefiting clients and losers.
8. Confusing Customers – complex pricing models.

CONCLUSION

In the modern, digital, global, civilized, Advanced, westernized world, the digital market and marketers, producers are in various techniques and advertisement, competitively reach the digital customers for occupying the markets for their company products, goods and services. It may be consumer goods, electronic goods, company products, ect..... Now a days it's a difficult to enter the market and take a sizeable shape in a short period. Now a days I tbrings new opportunities, access, transparency in marketing operations. Using of Digital market in the urban and rural areas.

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